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*Master's Degree in
International Science*

*Digital Nationalism and Neo-Techno-Nationalism: a study
of China's gaming industry*

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Introduction

Nationalism constitutes a complex multi-layered topic in the field of social studies that involves certain disjunctures between dimensions of politics, sociology and culture. According to a society's major socio-political trends, nationalism can change and take different forms. Given that the attempt to build a patriotic nation-building narrative is a significant component of the Chinese leadership's political agenda, any study of the social changes occurring in contemporary China cannot be separated from investigating the role that nationalism is playing in this regard. As the effects of such projection of nationalistic values can be variously observed in the Chinese economy, mass media discourse and in the behavior of ordinary citizens, this paper focuses on video games as one of a variety of mediums in the entertainment field involved in the transmission of a specific Chinese national identity and in the emergence of a nationalistic policymaking approach to technology.

In this research the study of video games has to be seen as the focus on a limited part of a wider phenomenon involving other forms of entertainment in the Chinese pop culture such as music, television, or movies that are affected by the Chinese Communist Party's (CCP) policies as well as a widespread nationalistic culture. In order to explain how and why nationalism manifests itself in the Chinese video games industry, I build on to two theoretical concepts: Digital Nationalism (DN) and Neo-Techno-Nationalism (NTN). They are here used to examine different aspects of the interconnections between video games, the State's nationalistic political agenda and economic interests based on the context in which they are consumed, developed and regarded in China.

Although in this view video games are only one of the possible subjects of analysis to scholars interested in the study of nationalism in the Chinese cultural industry, they are herein considered as worthy of particular attention. The first reason for this special focus is that there is a broad consensus around the fact that video games are more capable than traditional forms of broadcast media of influencing people's emotional states, thought patterns, and perceptions. According to Ian Bogost (2007), professor of media studies at the Georgia Institute of Technology, it is their interactive nature that makes video games an inherently persuasive medium. This type of immersive gaming experience, Bogost claims, allows players to create abstract mental models of how reality works and to form judgments about those models during the act of playing. Any media with such a persuasive nature is certainly to be looked at with interest for the communicative potential it holds.

Such evidence makes even more noteworthy the success of the most popular type of games in China, which is called massively multiplayer online role-playing games (MMORPGs), meaning games in which a gamer assumes the role of a character through which being able to interact with a great number of other gamers within a persistent game world. Hence, by their very interactive and participative nature, MMORPGs can play a significant role in representing ideological images, building social connections, learning cultural meaning, and contributing to the process of identity formation of their hundreds of thousands of enthusiastic gamers. This premise would already be enough to suggest, at the very least, that many of the factors involved in a video game's production, from its design to the narrative used in the story, are to be considered as an intentional choice of the producers beyond their entertaining purpose.

This incredible potentiality also explains the ongoing debate around the topic of game addiction experienced by gamers, especially in young age. Video game addiction has been a major concern for Chinese policymakers since the early emergence of these technologies. As a response to the high pressure put on them by both the government and parents, this challenge has been addressed with several measures by gaming companies, including real-name registration, an anti-addiction system and anti-fatigue software integrated within games as controls for game content and use (Jiang, Fung, 2017). As a matter of fact, even if the CCP has realized the potential of video games as a valuable tool to communicate its desired social and cultural values and foster economic growth, it doesn't mean that the promotion of the domestic video game industry is motivated by the intention of nurturing any sort of ideological assimilation. On the contrary, social values are also given a high priority alongside economic prosperity. The government's heavy-handed policies in the game industry in China seem to be quite justified by a series of controversial issues revolving around the compromise of the gamer's social life, as a result of which the public usually tends to support and even demand specific regulations designed to eradicate the negative effects of online gaming (Tsui, 2005).

The relevance of the video games industry in today's China is also supported by its growing economic weight and potential. In recent times entertainment and creative industries have been identified as increasingly important for economic growth. As China often identifies itself as a developing country due to its very recent although fast economic rise, it is worth mentioning that the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) acknowledges cultural industries as a key sector for job creation, innovation and trade capable

of stimulating economic growth (UNCTAD, 2010). The credibility of this conclusion is also shown by the extraordinary worldwide success of American cultural goods. The consumption of such products is in fact increasingly demanded abroad and contributes to the United States' soft power on other countries. In China, the video game market already is a growth market among the most successful ones and the trend doesn't seem to slow down. According to the data provided by Feng Shixin, deputy director of the editorial office of the Central Propaganda Department, the Chinese videogame supply chain generates an annual income of about 30 billion dollars, mainly due to the work of about 6,000 companies, including 200 public subsidiaries (Niko Partners, 2019). The Chinese flagship of this prominent sector certainly is Tencent, one of the most influential and profitable companies in the world and face of the Chinese power in the tech field. The CCP is closely connected to the company and often appoints Tencent as distributor of new products, like new video games and gaming consoles. If the impressive economic value of the Chinese gaming industry in itself is not enough to consider it worth of further study, the fact that it has been partly fostered by the government makes it worth investigating the reasons beyond these investments and how much they have to do with the will of the Chinese's leadership to build and define the country's own global identity and narrative.

One further reason for the analysis of the Chinese video game industry to be considered particularly revealing in the study of modern China is that, despite all the above-mentioned political, economic and social factors, there are very few studies on the topic. Specifically, we lack any thorough academic literature that actually addresses the study of the Chinese gaming industry comprehensively and from a socio-political perspective. Unlike other prominent video game world giants like the United States, Japan or Korea, on which consolidated literature and research already exists, the potentiality of the Chinese video game market with respect to the country's nationalistic narrative still remains widely unexplored by scholars. Other than just the lack of academic attention on the topic that certainly suggested to conduct this research, it was also motivated by the hope that it could be able to stimulate further studies, as the research work outlined hereafter is not comprehensive and exhaustive enough to cover the chosen field of study.

The main purpose of this paper is thus to investigate how video games can be a vehicle for new forms of nationalism and delineate the characteristics of those forms in the Chinese case. Specifically, I analyze the Chinese gaming industry and propose one specific game as a case study to establish a connection between contemporary nationalism in China and video games

as a relevant digital media. The paper starts with defining the concepts of Online Nationalism and Neo-techno-Nationalism and reviewing the related literature. This first chapter also provides for their application in the video game field through two case studies from other countries. The next chapter illustrates the Chinese video game market by providing both an historical and economic framework to explain how it has developed over the years, describe its present characteristics and investigate their compliance with the concepts of DN and NTN. In the third chapter, I then provide an empirical case of a specific Chinese video game, namely *Glorious Mission*. I explain how the game lends itself to the application of Online Nationalism and Neo-techno-Nationalism in the Chinese gaming industry by describing its narrative and gameplay and by contextualizing its developing process. Finally, I present the conclusions of the research, meaning the suitability of Online Nationalism and Neo-techno-Nationalism as theoretical foundations to analyze China's online game industry. Through an outline of this paper's findings, I will explain why it provides an excellent example of the interaction between new technologies and politics in a globalized and nationalistic China, which results in the projection and promotion of nationalistic ideologies. The conclusions will also include some potential points of interests for further research in this and other related fields of study.

1. Literature review and theoretical foundation

While a review of the burgeoning literature on nationalism is beyond the scope of this research, it is appropriate to at least provide a general overview of the literature related to the role of digital technologies in the emergence of new forms of nationalism. Even though the specific nature of this correlation needs to be further investigated, the explanatory value of its study is now widely acknowledged by scholars and a significant body of search has been produced on this topic. Social media platforms, for example, have recently been identified as able to encourage nationalistic sentiments to such an extent that they are believed to have played a crucial role in key political events such as the withdrawal of the United Kingdom (UK) from the European Union (EU) or Donald Trump's election as the United States' (US) President (Kreis, 2017). Consequently, an increasing number of studies have been focusing on the new ways in which technology affects the users' ideology but also on how different cultures, in turn, can influence technology's adoption and consumption in as many modalities (Kozinets, 2008; Jiang 2012; Schneider, 2018; Wu, 2007).

Nationalism scholars, as well as media and communication scholars, argued that digital technology created new forms of nationalism that are not necessarily as obvious or passionate as we might imagine, but rather banal and grounded in everyday configurations of digital communication (Billing, 1995; Fox and Miller-Idriss, 2008; Malesevic, 2019). Furthermore, while we might think of the internet as a purely abstract, globalized virtual environment, many studies have proved this assumption wrong. Despite the non-territorial nature of the internet, scholars demonstrated that geographic national borders are actually transferred on the Web and that users still maintain a common sense of national identity when they use online platforms (Eriksen, 2007). Halavais (2000), for example, contributed to shed light on the persistent national architecture of the digital world by showing that the majority of American websites always link to other websites hosted within the borders of the US instead of other countries.

This increasing interest on digital forms of nationalism led to the introduction and increasing application of the concepts of Digital Nationalism (DN) and Neo-Techno-Nationalism (NTN). In this chapter the two concepts will be defined and analyzed in two distinct sections, while also reviewing the relevant literature sources and arguing how they can be applied to the Chinese video game industry. At the end of the chapter I will provide

two case studies, respectively from the American and Indonesian video game industry, in order to add an empirical anchoring to the concepts.

1.1 Digital Nationalism

The terms “Online Nationalism” and “Digital Nationalism” are often used interchangeably by scholars interested in the promotion of nationalistic sentiments in digital forms. I choose to employ exclusively the second term, since I found that it is used more frequently in the relevant literature and it allows to deliver a more general meaning by referring to a wider range of media and entertainment forms that not necessarily involve the use of internet but are nevertheless relevant in the study of nationalism.

A general starting point to delineate the concept of DN is the definition provided by Zulkarnain (2014) as “a new mode of expressing national consciousness through the mediation of digital technologies”. More specifically, he refers to the production of content involving a country’s history, culture and traditions to encourage nationalistic fervour through the use of digital technologies. The dynamics of this phenomenon is not as simple as a cause-effect phenomenon, but rather it has to be seen as a form of nationalism resulting from a complex process of identity formation in everyday occurrences. The nature of DN is thus multifaced and can be explained by looking at the various ways in which digitalization changed communication and the user’s learning mechanism.

Mihelj and Martínez (2019) suggest that the greater level of participation and diversification characterizing digital media communication is a key element to describe how nationalism manifests itself in new ways compared to traditional forms. The specific nature and accessible cost of modern technology, in fact, entail the participation of a higher number of actors in public debates. In some cases this implies the weakening of the state’s attempt to sustain a dominant version of the national identity, but it doesn’t mean that digital platforms are neutral tools, immune to the influence of authorities. On the contrary, they undergo a process of moderation and selection that determines the content we can access online and the choices we are offered in the technology market. In countries with a prevalent authoritarian approach from the government this results in a one-to-many type of communication online involving the use of standardized language, recurring symbols and ideologies that facilitate the attempt to design the discourse on the nation (Schneider, 2018). In the case of China, for example, the CCP used the concept of “public opinion guidance” to describe its approach

towards national culture and media governance, a policy that consists of a mix of Leninist doctrines and media liberalization policies.

Political communication in a digital environment also implies the tendency of users to follow and tap on sources which match their pre-existent political attitudes. Although this selective exposure to specific political content is not a new element introduced by digital technologies, they certainly strengthen this trend and lead to the emergence of virtual “filter bubbles” (Mihelj and Martínez, 2019). The majority of modern digital platforms are in fact designed to work through algorithms that mainly expose people to material that they already like or agree with, notably the case of social media platforms such as Facebook or search engines like Google. The content accessible online, in fact, is not just the result of the state’s moderation but also of the influence of other actors with the power and resources to produce and orientate content on a large scale. Hence, as digital media are increasingly used as both sources of information and entertainment, their capacity to polarize political opinions can be exploited to create “ideological echo chambers”. By so doing, users are immersed in recurring digital infrastructures while hardly realizing the lack of more varied contents. In such a specifically designed and controlled environment, digital form of nationalism can easily proliferate. In the specific field of video games, this model of DN is observed in the analysis of video games’ software mechanism, visual representation, narrative construction and genre (Zulkarnain, 2014). In video games characterized by a nationalistic content, this exposure to reproductions of nationhood leads players to share certain political sentiments more easily and creates a sense of community and national solidarity. As a successful medium of cultural expression, video games shifted from a mere form of entertainment to contemporary learning tools in which players are like residents of a virtual world they interact with on a daily basis.

In recent years the player’s sense of national belonging is furtherly fostered in the “real world”, especially in Asian countries, with the organization of eSports. They consist of computer gaming competitions which can take place on a national level with players competing to achieve a national championship title, or with the participants representing their countries in international competition just like athletes in traditional sport events. The East-Asian eSports culture started out in Korea in the mid-nineties and has been growing in popularity ever since. However, unlike the United States and Europe where competitive gaming is usually associated with First Person Shooting (FPS) games, in Asian countries MMORPG games significantly prevailed. The growing success of these events led to the increase of studies on the subject, many of which have shown that eSports are connected to

the emergence of new symbolic meanings associated to specific national cultures, identities and shared norms and values (Seo, 2016).

Another easily recognizable form of DN in video games is the large use military simulation technology. The history of video games is in fact tied to a long legacy of documented militaristic inclination that remains relevant event today and is connected to the huge popularity of the war game genre (Zulkarnain, 2014). The logic underlying the design of these games is widely recognized as the ideological promotion of national values through the use of a “good versus evil” type of narrative and through the “gamification” of war. Academic studies in this field have been particularly numerous with regard to the American video game industry, which has produced a few of the most popular war games worldwide and notoriously made use of military designed technologies. In fact, in the US the military has actually developed war games to be used mainly as combat simulations and directly provided their own software used for military training to gaming companies for commercial use, but the opposite also occurs. A notorious case is the tactical simulator Marine Doom, which was developed for the US Marines from the FPS game series Doom (Derby, 2014). On a narrative level, war games represent a perfect example of DN as they serve the purpose of encouraging nationalistic sentiments and justify the country’s military interventions. These stories usually involve Americans or western soldiers as the heroes who fight for a good cause while the enemy is one that poses a existential threat to Western ideology (Sainsbury, 2016), which explains the particularly abundant production of war games set during World War II.

1.2 Neo-Techno-Nationalism

The term Neo-Techno-Nationalism was coined by Yamada (2000) as a further development of the concept of Techno-nationalism, defined as the deployment of public policies designed to provide governmental support to domestic firms operating in strategic high-tech industries in order to strengthen their competitiveness at an international level. Techno-nationalism in literature is in fact used in contrast with the concept of Techno-globalism, which refers to the globalization of technology as a force inevitably leading to a switch from the classic zero-sum game to a positive-sum game in international relations, in which all nation cooperate to sustain global economic growth. Yamada introduced the term Neo-Techno-Nationalism to describe a trend closer to the contemporary reality, meaning a policy which is an hybrid of the two previous concepts and is generated in response to the challenges posed by the globalization of technology in an attempt by nations to support their

own national interests. The concept of NTN appears to be very useful to address the economic implications of the use of digital technologies with a nationalistic intent while also widening the perspective of the research to a global scale. Unlike Digital Nationalism, NTN focuses on the external dimension of a country's nationalistic strategy to support tech-related industries and is strictly related to the relationship with other countries. Notably, it refers to the development of new policies aiming to leverage globalization to induce the inflow of cutting-edge foreign technologies in the domestic market and, by doing so, also fostering technical innovation domestically. This process involves a selection of these technologies, which must be congruent with the government's developmental goals, and a strong state commitment to mobilize resources and develop key technologies.

This is a fundamental feature of NTN that perfectly lends itself to the Chinese context, where the government intervention in a state-led economy is motivated by the necessity to induce more innovation and boost economic growth (Shim and Shin, 2016). Furthermore, in China NTN policies are also functional to the country's political ambition to enhance its international status and move beyond its status of "world's factory" with the reduction of its dependency on foreign technologies, promotion of exports and the use of bilateral bargaining, industrial diversification, and domestic structural adjustment (Jiang, Fung, 2017). This extends to the search for cultural independence in contrast to what is often perceived by Chinese officials as cultural invasion. In Asia, in fact, is not unlikely to associate globalization to the ideological and cultural penetration from Western countries and the gaming industry is inevitably involved in this process as one of the currently most successful form of cultural entertainment. The Chinese Original Online Games Offshore Popularization Plan by General Administration of Press and Publication (GAPP), for example, offers specific incentives to help Chinese games "go global rapidly" and has helped Chinese online games to become increasingly more popular in the Asian market (Jiang, Fung, 2017).

Nevertheless, unlike Techno-nationalism policies in which the government is the only driving force of technological development and Techno-globalism policies that see the private sector as the only promoter of innovation, NTN once again stands in the middle. As countries like China clearly show, governments have not disappeared or withdrawn as leading actors, but at the same time they had to redefine their roles in light of the growing importance of the private sector, thus building new infrastructures based on the partnership between public and private (Yamada, 2000). These partnerships have been implemented globally by governments in different ways: in Japan with government-sponsored research programs like the Very Large

Scale Integrated Circuit (VSLI), a project co-funded by the Ministry of International Trade and Industry (MITI) and private firms; in the United States with the Advanced Technology Program (ATP), designed to support the creation and commercialization of highly innovative technologies that are expected to benefit national economy; in Europe with bottom-up shared programs such as EUREKA, in which member countries can propose collaborative projects involving at least two private partners.

Another characteristic of NTN is the increased openness towards foreign entities to government-funded R&D programs, although their participation is often limited by specific conditions and requirements such as the presence of the firms' production facilities within the country (Yamada, 2000). This openness extends to the import of foreign high-tech products in the domestic market, which is nevertheless as selective and limited according to the government's strategy. In the case of the Chinese video game market the increased opening to foreign products of recent years has involved both Western and Asian games, but to different extents. American games, for example, not only are less imported than games from South Korea, but also seem to be less appealing to Chinese audience. Interviews conducted with Chinese gamers (Fung, 2010, 2017) showed that worldwide popular American games such as *World of Warcraft* are considered less pleasing on the aesthetic level, while Korean games are found to be more compatible to the Asian taste. On the contrary, Japanese games are generally more "westernized" both in the narrative and design, which explains their huge success in the American and European markets more than the Chinese one. Furthermore, South Korean games not only meet the aesthetic Chinese taste, but their production process is also strategically adapted to the political logics of the Chinese market. In order to prevent the transfer of core technologies and protect intellectual property rights, in fact, Western gaming companies usually find a Chinese distribution operator that allows them to stay the top of the industry chain. Conversely, Korean companies often establish their headquarters or local branches in China and thus benefit of a faster access to the market for their games. Hence, despite the generally higher openness, more space is given to regional players which perform better in the Chinese market in virtue of a perceived sense of regional cultural proximity (Jiang, Fung, 2017). This suggests that in NTN the cooperation with foreign entities is essential, but it is adapted to the nationalistic priorities of policy-makers.

1.3 Non-Chinese case studies: *Nusantra Online* and *Call of Duty*

The following two cases from outside China have the purpose to further illustrate the existing literature and show how video games can be powerful and effective mediums of Digital Nationalism. The first one is Zulkarnain's analysis of the Indonesian video game *Nusantra Online*, which represents a very accurate and unique example of DN and NTN from an Asian country. The author also uses the term "playable nationalism" with reference to the specific characteristics of the media at hand.

The game's narrative is based on a revised version of the Indonesian history: Nusantra is in fact an allegory of the country, a playful and imaginative version that offers the gamer an immersive nationalistic experience (Zulkarnain, 2014). According to Victor Junaidy, director of the game's developing company and its main programmer, the game's main goal is to offer an alternative to foreign titles in light of the growing concern over the cultural penetration in Indonesia by means of various media. The game's nationalistic mission and the creators' commitment to the development of its historical aspects seem to be a critical response to the consumption of foreign goods enhanced by globalization and even suggest the priority of their nationalistic sentiments over the interest towards any economic revenue.

In order to fulfill this goal, the design of *Nusantra Online* involves a "close-to-reality" game environment. For example, there are realistic representations of typically Indonesian plants and the architecture resembles the one of real historical buildings. As for the game's story, *Nusantra Online* is an idealized version of Indonesia and its history. The game's opening cutscene depicts Nusantra as a peaceful place that fell into war as a result of massive invasion from unspecified foreign force. Nevertheless, once the game goes on, the invasion element disappears. The gamer never encounters any invaders and none of the game's missions are related to the colonization aspect. Zulkarnain argues that this lack of correlation between the beginning of the game and its narrative progression can be explained by seeing the opening cutscene only as a symbol of the developers' concern over the penetration of foreign cultures, while the rest of the game is used as a call to "reconstruct" the nation into its ideal form. The absence of the invaders in the game is, instead, the attempt to build a fantasy on the origin of the Indonesian nation and at the same time provide a version of Indonesia to aspire to.

Nusantra Online is not a nationalistic product only in its narrative. The developers also came as far as developing their own game engine, namely Angel, which they promised to

release for free as an explicit attempt to provide an Indonesian-made software that can be used to improve the country's technological independence. Game engines can in fact be used in other contexts, since they can run on the same code base as other software systems (Bogost, 2006) and this would mean providing the Indonesian programming community with a free source code.

The second case study is far more famous and is related to an entire series of games. Its name is Call of Duty (COD), a FPS video game franchise by the American publisher Activision that started in 2003 and includes games set in World War II, Cold War and futuristic worlds. Among the initial main series, several spin-offs and games exclusively released on specific platforms or consoles, the franchise includes more than 30 games, with the latest one released in November, 2021. COD is one of the many titles that brought the narrative focus back on the US militarism in a post 9/11 America. As Gagnon (2010) argues, the game works as a rewriting tool for the American military intervention history by presenting specific a recurring narrative: the US are forced to fight evil enemies that have to be destroyed in order to protect the American people. The whole game series, Gagnon says, promotes a specific version of the post 9/11 geopolitics by exploiting the ongoing debate on national security. The story in Call of Duty: Modern Warfare (MW) for example, revolves around the US and British armies joining forces to fight against Imran Zakhaev, a Russian Ultranationalist whose goal is to bring his country back to the Soviet era. The direct sequel of the game is Call of Duty: Modern Warfare 2 (MW2) and is set five years later. In this game Vladimir Makarov, one of Zakhaev's allies, starts a terroristic war against the US and this eventually leads to the Russian invasion of America. These examples already suggest how the game's narrative is used to justify military violence as a response to hostility against America, depicting it as the "victim" which has no choice but defending itself (Bos, 2018). Furthermore, the historical representations included in the games generate specific cultural and political perceptions that tend to reflect the contemporary US geopolitical stance towards Russia, Central Asia and Middle East. In this respect, Call of Duty provides the gamers with the opportunity to assist American soldiers in their mission of defeating "virtual copies" of the US "real" enemies in the world (Ouellette, 2008).

The nationalistic nature of the COD series is also shown by the military equipment used in the games. The players can in fact use virtual versions of many existing weapons actually used by US soldiers in the real world, depicted in the games in the most realistic and accurate way possible both in their aesthetic and in their firing performance. Ian Bogost (2006)

proposed the concept of “procedural rhetoric”, described as the “practice of using processes persuasively, just as verbal rhetoric is the practice of using oratory persuasively and visual rhetoric is the practice of using images persuasively”. In line with this concept, COD provides the players with exhaustive knowledge of the best military tools and most importantly it makes them develop a preference to certain guns that the players will make their “weapons of choice.”

While *Nusantra Online* is the product of a relatively small start-up that doesn't seem to have any ties with the government, COD is one of the biggest gaming franchises in the world and benefits from the US actual military power. Despite this difference, in both *Nusantra Online* and the *Call of Duty* series the players are given an idealized and revised version of the story that fits a certain nationalistic view of Indonesia and the United States. Both cases show how the interactive and simulative nature of video games perfectly lends itself to the promotion of a desired national identity, in accordance with the concept of Digital Nationalism.

2. The Chinese video game market

In the video game market, China's Neo-Techno-Nationalism is the product of the combination of the choices and perceptions of all the participating stakeholders, meaning the party-state, State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs), private businesses and a public of both gamers and non-gamers. Nevertheless, the market's present features were also determined by the deep socio-economic transformations occurring in China over the last decades. Its evolution from a socialist society of collective ownership and economic equality to one with growing capitalistic logics of private accumulation, consumerism, and openness to foreign entities reveals China's new way of pursuing its nationalistic goals. In many cases, this new way clashes with the country's own traditional social values and creates complex social contradictions. Video games in China are an example of this dynamic, as they have always been as promoted and successful as much as they have been demonized and controlled (Zhang, 2013), and gamers themselves have been variously seen as modern patriotic idols on the one hand, and as addicted or victims of the industry, on the other. To provide a grasp of this apparently contradictory political and cultural discourse around video games in China and explain how it reveals two sides of the same coin (i.e. its NTN), it is necessary to analyze these contradictions within the historical context of the country. Similarly to other new media technologies such as television or film, the narrative about video games is still very contentious and shows that China's NTN policies in this field is dualistic in nature.

2.1 Historical background

As an imported media technology, the early stage of the Chinese video game market development saw the absolute dominance of foreign players as the result of two main factors: the 1970s economic strategy of "reform and opening-up" led by Deng Xiaoping and the lack of domestic technological innovation (Zhang, 2013; Kshetri, 2009). Deng's reform, often referred to as the "open-door policy", reveals China's strong tradition of self-reliant techno-nationalism meeting a new interest in techno-globalism trends (Jian and Fung, 2017). It was the beginning of a new way to conceive the country's nationalistic ambitions, perfectly explained by a famous Deng Xiaoping's quote: "No matter if it is a white cat or a black cat; as long as it can catch mice, it is a good cat."¹ Under the new policies, in fact, China moved away from a strategy of economic self-sufficiency to become an active participant of the

¹ From the original quote in Chinese: "不管黑猫白猫，捉到老鼠就是好猫".

world market and of international economic organizations. The aim was to modernize the country by “learning from the West”, meaning by importing knowledge and technology to narrow the economic gap with foreign powers. A crucial point of this nationalistic strategy, however, was that it wouldn’t imply a subjugation to the Western world but rather it would exploit it to develop China’s own economic and military power while maintaining the Chinese traditional cultural and political system (Huan, 1986).

This very same line of policy will be a constant of China’s relations with new technologies, including video games. One of the main features of Deng’s policy was the creation of Special economic zones (SEZs), where the government allowed the introduction of more free market-oriented economic policies in contrast with an entirely planned economy in the rest of mainland China. In the post-Maoist society, between the mid-1980s and the early 1990s the prevailing trend among the first private business owners that were interested in seizing the opportunity given by the SEZs and the import of new technologies were the linguistic and cultural localization of foreign products and, in the specific case of video games, the manufacturing of game cartridges and software (Pan, 1993). The predominant gaming platforms imported in this initial stage were street arcades and home consoles. Nevertheless, since they were introduced in the market adopting distinct marketing strategies, they met different reactions from a Chinese society still deeply embedded with traditional socialist values such as collectivism and frugality (Zhang, 2013). Arcade games on the one hand became a popular product of pure entertainment and socialization for young people, but for their lack of utility they were accused of alienating kids from study and work duties and labeled as potentially pathological. More generally, arcades became scapegoats for the growing consumerism and moral decay. Game consoles on the other hand were welcomed, as they were imported in China under the falsified format of “education software” for young consumers.

The electronics company Subor is considered one of the first Chinese businesses to understand the importance and take advantage of the commercial advertising in these years, and in particular to promote their copy of Nintendo’s Famicom, called Subor Video Game System or Xiǎo Bàwáng². The device was launched as a “computer study machine” designed to teach kids how to type while also entertaining them, but basically it just consisted of a game console accessorized with a keyboard. By selling games as playful educative systems, Subor addressed the parents’ concern about their kids’ computer literacy, whose importance

² In Chinese characters 小霸王, which can be translated as “Little Emperor.”

was prescribed by Deng Xiaoping himself, while simultaneously using innovative marketing strategies like choosing the emergent martial arts movie star Jackie Chan as a sponsor for the advertising of *Xiǎo Bàwáng*. Through this innovative step, the console became synonymous of the patriotic push towards the modernization of society and paved the way for the success of video games as a tool for the country's nationalistic goals. For the first time, a new discourse around the benefits of video games emerged and became the foundation of the China's future NTN strategies in the field.

Despite the positive attitude towards game consoles, a general prejudice remained among parents and the party-state officials, who defined the digital entertainment culture as a “malicious bourgeois tumor” and only tolerated video games as instrumental to the state's aim to modernize the country (Zhang, 2013). Nevertheless, after Deng's Southern Excursion in 1992 and his famous statement “To get rich is glorious”, the PC games industry emerged and flourished in China, along with a surge in home computer ownership and new gaming-related jobs. This first generation of digital technology enthusiasts belonged to the urban elites and were often greatly celebrated as patriotic pioneers for their contribution to the development of a national Chinese gaming industry that could finally face foreign competitors, even though this wasn't enough to ease their opponent's call for more control and regulation upon the pathological risks of video games.

In the 1990s PC games imported from Japan, US, Europe and Taiwan still dominated the Chinese market. The general concern over the perceived Western cultural invasion led to a change in the discourse around the pathological nature of video games, which was now attributed to their foreign origin more than the media itself. This new perception, in addition to the need to promote domestic technological innovation and preserve indigenous cultural tradition, further enhanced a stronger nationalistic mentality towards games. Moreover, China's entry in the WTO in 2001 posed new challenges for Chinese domestic industries facing greater foreign competitions (Jiang and Fung, 2017). In general, globalization facilitated the importation and consumption of Western entertainment goods, thus further increasing the anxiety over the need to stimulate the production of an indigenous cultural industry. Hence, in these years Chinese video games started to include anti-imperialist topics or narratives related to Chinese traditional culture (Zhang, 2013) as their impact was greatly revalued from a political perspective as well. The China Communist Youth League (CCYL), for example, deployed them as platforms to strengthen young players' “national spirit” (Kshetri, 2009).

Despite these changes, however, video games were still largely identified as extrinsic to socialist values. In fact, the educational benefits that initially led to the popularity of game consoles faded away and were totally supplanted by their entertaining purpose. All the above mentioned socio-economic changes that gave video games a new nationalistic value started to collide with the pathological view on this media, generating a duality that is a key component of NTN in China. Both the strong will to pursue economic success on the one hand and the concern over the protection of traditional values from potential foreign influence on the other, arose from nationalistic sentiments that have driven China’s policies towards the gaming industry from this initial stage on.

2.2 Recent developments and regulations

Since the early 2000s the Chinese online games industry started to grow exponentially, with Massive Multiplayer Online Games (MMOGs) dominating on other genres. The Chinese gaming market has quickly overcome other countries’ by size and sales volume, surpassing South Korea’s market in 2006 and thus becoming the biggest online gaming market in Asia. With such an undeniable potential, the even persisting and widespread concern over video games’ pathological effects started to be seen as economically counterproductive by a growing part of the public opinion. This duality of views is embedded in China’s NTN policies that gave to the gaming market its peculiar features distinguishing it from other countries to this day.

Figure 1 - Growth in Number of Online Gamers.
Source: China Internet Network Information Center (CNNIC)

While in industrialized countries like Japan, South Korea and USA the market was strongly dominated by the biggest console-based platforms (Sony's PlayStation, Microsoft's Xbox and Nintendo's Wii), that same type of high-priced, retail, packaged game sales was not successful in China. Not only Chinese gamers were unable or unwilling to pay this much for a single game, but the high rate of piracy for packaged games discouraged foreign companies from trying to penetrate the Chinese market with the same business model (The Economist, 2008). Furthermore, as part of the nationalistic goal to exploit foreign resources to enhance the development of domestic capabilities, the Chinese game industry has made great use of imported technology and formats, especially from the Korean games. Because of their cultural affinity, Korean games are very popular in China and many Chinese companies experienced an incredible growth by making game adaptations or clones based on Korean models. This trend also extended to the acquisition of intellectual property, to the point that only in 2005 China actually paid 117.4 million dollars in royalties to Korean game developers (Bremner, 2006).

Government's regulations and policies are another distinctive element of China's gaming industry. The interest in developing new technologies and strengthening the country's competitiveness along with a strong concern over national security and gaming addiction have been driving the Chinese political action, increasingly revealing the dualistic nature of the NTN's strategy. On the one hand, Beijing has been providing additional governmental support with measures such as the Chinese National High Technology Development Program, also called the 863 Program after its date of establishment³. Initially endorsed by Deng Xiaoping, the program was reevaluated and implemented in 2001 under the Tenth Five-Year Plan to address a number of cutting-edge high-tech issues of strategic importance and boost industrial competitiveness. Furthermore, recognizing the need for indigenous innovation, China has also implemented policies to offer attractive incentives to foreign companies to relocate their R&D facilities (Jiang and Fung, 2017). The same nationalistic interest in technological advancement that pushes for the supply of foreign resources without strictly depending on them also applies to the gaming market, where foreign players are not allowed to release their games independently in the country but foreign financial capital, joint ventures, and R&D cooperation with Chinese companies are largely encouraged.

The strategic relevance of the game industry has been underlined by Chinese officials such as Wu Shulin, deputy director of the General Administration of Press and Publication

³ March 1986, 86/3 by the Chinese date format.

(GAPP, in Chinese 中华人民共和国新闻出版总署), who stated that the government has included online gaming in the 2006-2010 plan for software and information service development and intended to support the development of the industry (People's Daily, 2006). Coherently with the NTN core feature to increase innovation while still limiting external influence, this support from Beijing's authorities has often resulted in a major barrier to foreign players. Since 2000 China has had an official ban on the sales and manufacturing of game consoles over concerns of moral corruption (Kshetri, 2009), allowing even big foreign companies such as Sony and Nintendo to only operate in the Shanghai Free Trade Zone (FTZ). This ban has only been lifted in 2015, enabling foreign companies to manufacture and sell anywhere in the country (The Wall Street Journal, 2015).

However, highly rigid restrictions are still applied to the video game market. In order to enter in China video games must be included in the list of approved games by the GAPP and the general approval guidelines are provided by the Ministry of Information Industry (MII, in Chinese 中华人民共和国工业和信息化部), which is also responsible for the promotion of Chinese telecommunications and software companies. Even if these selection criteria are not clearly outlined or made known, the resulting choices suggest that they are based on nationalistic principles. As a matter of fact, while games made in China easily survive State censorship, only a few foreign games get the approval to access the Chinese market every year (Jiang and Fung, 2017). Just to mention a recent example, among the 989 video games that have received licenses by GAPP in 2019 only 30 were foreign titles. Since July 2021 the GAPP has suspended the approval of new gaming licenses and the freeze has recently been extended to the whole year 2022. Even though no official explanation has been provided, the decision comes just a few months after President Xi Jinping raised the issue of gaming and internet addiction during the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference in March 2021 (SCMP, 2021).

The pathological effects of video games clearly remain a strong component of the debate that sees two nationalistic argumentations at odds: the interest in the development of the industry for economic purposes against the need to keep its social side effects under control. The growing number of users playing online games, in fact, intensified the pre-existing concern around gaming addiction and moral deviance. If on the one hand China's NTN led to the promotion of the gaming industry as part of its nationalistic ambition of economic success, on the other it also caused the establishment of new restrictions as a response to the urge to preserve the traditional socialist values by which the collective good

prevails on the individual choice. Instead of investigating the possible root causes of such pathological behavior from a sociological point of view, Beijing's measures against internet and gaming addictions have focused on the material use of video games, identifying the problem with the device itself. Recent developments along these lines include Beijing's decision in 2019 to forbid game playing between 10 p.m. to 8 a.m. and limitations on the amount of money that minors could spend on gaming items each month. In addition, in August 2021 a daily gaming time limit of three hours was introduced for minors. According to GAPP, these new limitations are a direct response to growing concern that games affected the children's health (Reuters, 2021). However, by the superficial nature of these measures, there are several doubts about their long term effectiveness on online gaming addiction. One main reason of skepticism is that video games are only one of the many entertainment sources people can access to online, including livestreaming platforms. Short-video apps such as Douyin and Kuaishou, for example, are extremely popular in China and their use is now greatly diversified. They turned into huge e-commerce platforms where streamers advertise products, but they are also used as gameplay streaming platforms which became very popular among young Chinese gamers (China Communications, 2021). As their gaming time was reduced by the government's new measures, a growing number of children started to spend more time watching or creating those gameplay clips (SupChina, 2021). Nevertheless, the government's restrictions have only been targeting the online game market without acknowledging those implications.

Despite the tightening of restrictions and the contentious ongoing debate on the matter, the Chinese game industry is expanding both domestically and abroad. The Global Games Market Report produced by Newzoo in 2020 shows that the Chinese games market is the largest in the world, both by revenues and by number of players, particularly for mobile games. The same report also shows that, of the total 124.5 billion dollars generated by the top 50 Gaming companies worldwide in 2019, the Chinese giant Tencent ranked number one. Another significant example of the industry's success is *Genshin Impact*, a game developed by the Chinese company miHoYo, which in 2020 marked the biggest international launch in history for a Chinese game. According to data from a Newzoo 2021 report, *Genshin Impact* performed exceptionally well across mobile, console, PC, and video-streaming platforms. Further data from the tracking firm Sensor Tower show that in the first week after its launch the game generated 60 million dollars on mobile devices alone, becoming the world's second-highest-grossing mobile game. Moreover, Chinese industry leaders like Tencent and NetEase

are now successful enough to invest more resources in overseas markets and opening new development subsidiaries abroad. This serves not only to expand their business but also as a way to cope with the difficulties of drawing up new video gaming projects in the domestic market due to the governmental restrictions (SCMP, 2021).

The dominating business model that generates such high revenues has also been subjected to high criticism. The majority of the most popular games in China, including *Genshin Impact*, use a revenue system called *gacha*, a monetization mechanism that involves the purchase of a random selection of virtual items in the form “loot boxes” and is often referred to with the more general term “microtransactions”. The type of item acquirable is extremely varied, going from different customization options of the characters to game’s equipment. In some games the boxes can also be received for free with the accomplishment of the game’s objectives, but the purchase usually involves higher chances to receive rare items, if not exclusive ones that cannot be received in other ways. Many games of this kind are labeled “pay to win”, as they provide significant additional advantages to gamers that pay for them. This system is often used with games that can be started and played for free, but the free gaming options are usually pretty limited and thus gaming companies periodically release purchasable new content as game updates. As the nature of this mechanism has been compared to gambling, it drew enough concern to force many gaming companies to take some mild measures, such as warning players over the actual odds of winning rare items (SCMP, 2019).

What emerges from this overview is that the impressive success of the video game industry in China has always grown in parallel with the deep-rooted fear of the social risks posed by their use. From the nationalistic perspective that priorities the economic prosperity of the country but at the same is attentive towards the preservation of traditional social values, both perceptions are legitimate. This almost conflicting circumstances generate a demand for governmental action in both directions in the name of public interest, thus creating the dualistic nature that characterizes Chinese Neo-Techno-Nationalism. While it can be arguable if the measures adopted by the Chinese authorities to tackle gaming addiction are actually going to be enough to fix the issue, appease the general anxiety or definitively give legitimacy to the online game industry, an inversion of the positive economic performance of the game industry appears unlikely. The restrictions, in fact, don’t seem to be a suitable long term solution and only target a specific and limited field in the wider context of the relationship between addictive online technologies and the youth. The Chinese gaming industry and, in

general, China's economic rise are recent enough that they still need to cope with a society deeply entrenched with its most traditional moral values. The coexistence of two equally important nationalistic interest is more than likely going to drive China's NTN for the foreseeable future.

3. Case Study: Glorious Mission

In this chapter I will add an empirical evidence to my research on Digital Nationalism in the Chinese gaming industry by providing a specific case study. For this purpose I will examine the game *Guāngróng shǐmìng* (光荣使命), translated in English as *Glorious Mission*⁴. As the game has been released only in China and there are no relevant scholarly publications concerning it, part of the information that I will provide are my own English translations of primary sources that are available in Chinese only. My analysis covers the game's development as well as its narrative and gameplay characteristics, which all suggest a deliberate use of the medium to promote nationalistic values, encourage a favorable opinion of the Army and enhance the importance of national defense.

More specifically, I suggest that *Glorious Mission* is an attempt to create a virtual, immersive and yet playful setting to trigger the player's patriotic sentiments towards China. This sense of commitment to one's homeland in the game is particularly related to the safeguard of the nation in the traditional sense of military defense, but it also involves the defense of its historical dignity. The release of *Glorious Mission* has also been much debated, especially on Western media, with regard to its alleged use as a recruiting tool for the Chinese army to appeal young gamers, encourage them to join the armed forces and prepare them to actually fight for the country. However, in this paper this aspect will not be investigated further as I believe it to be highly speculative.

Figure 2 – Game poster.
Source: *Glorious Mission Official website (plagame.cn)*

⁴ Even though in some online sources the game is referred to as *Passion Leads Army*, I will henceforth use the name *Glorious Mission* as it is a more accurate translation of the original title.

3.1 Development and promotion

The role of the Chinese military in the development of *Glorious Mission* is probably the most significant factor to take into consideration. The first commercialized version of *Glorious Mission* was a first-person shooting computer game, proudly advertised as the first Chinese military-themed game. The title was developed by the Chinese online game company Giant Interactive (巨人网络) and distributed by Shanghai Taren Network Technology (上海塔人网络科技) in 2011. At the end of the same year, the People's Liberation Army (PLA), specifically the Nanjing Military Region, started to develop a new version of the game that was distributed among the troupes, reportedly as a virtual training simulator and for entertainment purposes, even though it was not available to the public. Only in August 2012 it was announced that the PLA's version would have been launched on the market as an upgrade of the original one with the name *Glorious Mission 1.5* or *Glorious Mission Online*.

The involvement of the Army had a strong impact on the game on different levels. As explained by different national media reporting the news, the contribution of PLA's army officers and soldiers served to bring the gameplay closer to reality by enriching it with more accurate details of military life and combat training. According to Xinhua, China's official state press agency, in the upgraded version the gaming battlefields were made more realistic through the use actual three-dimensional digital maps of some Chinese military regions' training fields. Other upgrades included changes to uniforms, vehicles and weapons which

Figure 3 – Screenshot of the game.
Source: *Glorious Mission* Official website (plagame.cn)

were made more similar to the ones actually used by the PLA in terms of both aesthetic and combat performance. For instance, the upgrade introduced as one of the possible fighting areas the Liaoning (in Chinese 辽宁舰, Liáoníng Jiàn), which is known to be the first aircraft carrier commissioned to the PLA's Army Navy Surface Force in those very years.

Nevertheless, the updates of *Glorious Mission 1.5* consisted in more than just a higher accuracy in the details related to the military equipment, they were also given an important representative value for the Army's prestige. On several news media, including the popular social media platform Weibo, the decision to release the PLA's version of the game was reported as an attempt to enhance China's national defense culture, especially among young people, through a successful promotion of the Chinese Army. To further mark this patriotic purpose, the game was officially launched on August 1st on the occasion of the Army Day or PLA Day (in Chinese 中国人民解放军建军纪念日), which celebrates the foundation of the PLA and in 2013 marked its 86th anniversary. Moreover, in a general national climate where digitalization and technological advancement equal to status and power enhancement, *Glorious Mission* was also a sign of the Army's will to modernize itself as it was used in a quite innovative context. In December 2013, in fact, the National University of Defense Technology held a three-days tournament called "Cup for the strongest Army division" (in Chinese 强军杯), a military gaming competition in which *Glorious Mission* was the platform of the contest to test the soldiers' strategic combat skills and their ability to organize and coordinate. There were thirteen participating teams coming from the hosting school, seven other military academies and three local universities (ScienceNet.cn, 2013). The competition was the first of this kind involving military institutions and universities.

Furthermore, in accordance with the nationalistic goal of increasing the Chinese gaming industry's competitiveness through technological innovation prescribed by Neo-techno-nationalism, the development of *Glorious Mission* was an attempt to create the first entirely Chinese-made military game that could compete with foreign homologues. In terms of technological advancement, for example, the game is the first one made in China to use the DirectX 11 interface for game programming software⁵. More importantly, Giant Interactive's main developer, Gu Kai, highlighted that *Glorious Mission* is a fully domestic project: from creative design to program development, it was entirely made through the cooperation between the Giant Interactive development team and the PLA's technical support and

⁵ Microsoft DirectX is a software technology designed to enhance multimedia experiences, particularly used in the field of video games developing. Direct X 11 was, in those years, the most advanced version.

simulations, thus its creators hold the intellectual property rights of the game (People's Daily, 2013). This aspect is particularly important in light of the nationalistic goal to reduce the reliance on foreign resources by developing China's own industry. Also, in order to reach the perfect level of accuracy, the creative team of *Glorious Mission* gathered elite professionals from all the fields and used the expertise of the Army. For example, Gu claims, the action capture process of the project involved top special forces of the Nanjing Military Region and the dubbing actors were selected among soldiers from the front-line troupes. Even the sound production team had top-class Chinese members, being led by the winner of the Golden Rooster Award and the Hong Kong Film Awards, Wang Tanrong.

Figure 4 – Screenshot of the game.
Source: *Glorious Mission* Official website (plagame.cn)

Glorious Mission, hence, was designed to embed the highest militaristic and patriotic values through a pervasive promotion of the Army. The use of the military-made technology, real combat simulations and the direct contribute of the troupes makes the game a sort of PLA's own promotional campaign. In addition, the primacy of being the first Chinese military-themed game and the pride of being technologically advanced enough to compete with international homologues perfectly fits with China's NTN strategy to exploit technology and globalization to enhance the country's status.

3.2 Narrative and content

From a narrative perspective, *Glorious Mission 1.5* offers a specific gameplay experience in which the culture of national defense and the honor that comes from protecting

the country deeply permeate the storyline. They are, in fact, the most recurring topics throughout the whole game and the gameplay system itself was specifically designed to incorporate those topics. Similarly to other foreign games of this genre such as *Call of Duty*, players can choose among several gaming modes, including a training mode, single-player campaign, Co-op modes, player versus player modes and special missions. Nevertheless, despite the military theme, the game rarely offers the possibility of a tactical approach to the mission and provides players with only one fixed path to the end of the gaming section (Reuters, 2013). Furthermore, the main focus of the story embodies one of the most sensitive matters of China's actual foreign politics, meaning the controversial relations with Japan and the territorial disputes that have become a centerpiece of diplomatic tensions between the two countries. The nationalistic perspective offered by the game on the matter emerges through several factors, including the language used and the chosen setting.

One of the expansions released for the Player versus Environment (PvE)⁶ mode, for example, is called *Dream to return to Shanghai* (梦回上海) and it is specifically referred to with the term Kàng-Rì (抗日). The term can be translated as “War of Resistance” and in Chinese is commonly used to refer to the Second Sino-Japanese War, a conflict that took place between 1937 and 1945 between the Republic of China (RoC) and the Empire of Japan and that resulted from Japan's expansionistic policies of that time. In general, it can be said that this conflict represents quite a sensitive historical issue in the relations between China and Japan. The reference to Kàng-Rì is not uncommon in the recent Chinese pop-culture, as it has often been topic of many Chinese dramas and movies that usually feature Japanese characters as antagonists and show the brutality of Japanese troops during the war (SCMP, 2013; Griese, 2015).

In terms of narrative contexts, this game expansion of *Glorious Mission* deliberately presents a scenario that lends itself to the nationalistic tone of the game. Players, in fact, fight as PLA soldiers against the Imperial Japanese Army during the battle historically known as Battle of Shanghai, and non without reason. Such battle was one of the largest and bloodiest of the entire Sino-Japanese conflict and it is often considered as the event that officially started World War II in Asia. As reported by the South China Morning Post, the official website of *Glorious Mission* sponsored the release of this special mission as an opportunity for players to “defend their homes and country” as well as “restoring history” in the spirit of

⁶ Also known as Player versus Enemy, it is used to refer to a gaming mode where players fight against computer-controlled enemies or have to explore the environment and survive its adversities.

“not forgetting ‘Century of Humiliation’”(in Chinese: 百年国耻). This expression is particularly used in the Chinese political discourse and refers to a period of 110 years starting in 1839, when Britain forced China’s rulers to open their ports to the opium trade and by so doing caused the beginning of the so-called First Opium War. This event marked China’s first exposure to the West and its subjugation to foreign powers, including Japan. China’s “little brother”, in fact, was military strong enough to gain control over Taiwan, some parts of Manchuria and further into China’s territory (Kaufman, 2010). For these historical reasons, Japan is often considered as one of the foreign invaders responsible of inflicting China such humiliation and motivating its search for redemption.

Another PvE expansion that sets the tone for the game’s nationalistic narrative towards Japan was given an even more special attention, as it was released as one of the main upgrades included in the launch of *Glorious Mission 1.5* in 2013. It is called *Protect the Diaoyu Islands* (保卫钓鱼岛) and involves an ongoing controversial dispute over a group of islands whose sovereignty is contended among China, Japan and Taiwan even today. The islands, located in the East China Sea between Taiwan and Okinawa, are known as the Senkaku Islands in Japan and the Diaoyu Islands in China and are considered one of the main causes of a growing and renewed anti-Japanese sentiment escalating in China precisely in those years. Prior to this exacerbation of relations, China’s leaders have always limited their policies on the Diaoyu Islands dispute to the reassertions of sovereignty and non-military actions. However, when in 2012 Tokyo Governor Shintaro Ishihara proposed that the Tokyo Prefecture would buy three of the islands in order to protect them, many Chinese netizens (in China called Wǎngmín, 网民) urged for a boycott of Japanese goods and started numerous street demonstrations across the country. The protests, however, were not only meant to protest against the Japanese Governor’s announcement but also to complain China’s lack of action on the matter (Gries, 2015). Following this outpouring of anti-Japanese and anti-government outrage, Beijing’s approach shifted from unarmed surveillance to the deployment of fully armed naval warships and the declaration of an air defense identification zone on the islands.

The release of *Protect the Diaoyu Islands*, therefore, coincidentally occurred when the contentious debate on the islands was at its strongest peak in years, thus benefitting from the prevailing public approval. The mission’s purpose of this special expansion, in fact, is to defend the Diaoyu Islands base from the Japan Self-Defense Forces, thus giving players the opportunity to fight the invaders back as if it would somehow rectify the actual historical

injustice experienced by China. Similarly to the *Dream to return to Shanghai* expansion, the symbolic importance of this historical context is emphasized by the creators themselves. As reported by the South China Morning Post, in fact, in a press release on *Glorious Mission* the Diaoyu expansion was defined as “the highlight of this update” and it was meant to send the message that “Japan must return our stolen territory.” Nevertheless, despite the obvious focus on this territorial dispute, Gu claimed that the decision to tie the mission with that specific topic was a response to growing public interest and not a political act (BBC, 2013).

The overall opinion resulting from the above analysis is that *Glorious Mission* provides an example of Digital Nationalism in the Chinese gaming industry. The strong focus on the military culture and the deeply nationalistic hint of the narrative, in fact, are not innovative per se but rather for the medium in which they are incorporated. It marks the first Chinese attempt to use a video game to pursue, in a more or less explicit way, multiple nationalistic goals: technological innovation, increased national competitiveness, promotion of the national identity and enhancement of the Army’s image.

Figure 5 – Screenshot of the game.
Source: *Glorious Mission* Official website (plagame.cn)

Conclusions

The purpose of this research is to investigate the interplay of China's nationalistic culture, interests and political agenda with the unique development of the country's gaming industry, based on the way video games are designed, distributed and consumed in contemporary China. With this in mind, I adopted the concept of Digital Nationalism (DN) in combination with Neo-Techno-Nationalism (NTN), as they seem to provide the most suitable theoretical framework to analyze the result of the above-mentioned correlation. Specifically, the focus on video games provides the opportunity to study the emergence of new forms of nationalism still widely unexplored, especially in the Chinese context. Although both notions were previously introduced and employed in the relevant literature to analyze the implications of the development of digital technologies on nationalism, they take in consideration different aspects of the phenomenon. For this reason, I saw in their combined use the possibility to outline an accurate and comprehensive picture of the Chinese video game industry and its peculiarities.

On the one hand, I used the concept of DN as it addresses the issue of the evolution of nationalism as a result of the specific characteristics of digital technologies, such as the access to greater public participation and the repetitive exposure to topics the users' find appealing. These features paved the way to the actualization of DN as the production of digital content and infrastructures that promote nationalistic values by using the specific cultural and historical distinctiveness of a certain country. Nevertheless, DN denotes nationalism in a format that doesn't necessarily involve its explicit and aggressive expression, but rather every day and banal forms which are easily accessible by using digital technologies. As an increasingly popular cultural media technology, video games incorporated DN by giving rise to interactive and playful forms of nationalism. Scholars in the social sciences have already produced a significant body of literature covering the correlation between nationalistic ideologies and videogames, which shows their effectiveness as an exceptionally persuasive media. Many studies have focused on the particularly prolific genre of war games, which is widely recognized as easily subjected to a functional employment in the promotion of nationalistic ideologies due to their peculiar gaming format and military-themed content. Their development, in fact, often involves the use of military designed simulation technology, specific narratives that encourage the formation of nationalistic ideals and not least immersive and competitive game mechanics.

A well known case of this kind is the worldwide famous American series *Call of Duty*, that fits this model of DN with its recurring application of a “good versus evil” type of narrative, in which the United States usually get involved in a conflict as the heroic side against a hostile foreign enemy that can only be stopped through military force. Such pattern serves the purposes of both legitimizing the US’ military action and promoting a narrative that supports the country’s actual geopolitical stand. Another case of DN which, however, lies outside the realm of military-themed games, is the Indonesian *Nusantra Online*. According to its own creators, in fact, the game was specifically developed with the goal to counteract the cultural penetration from foreign countries, which increased precisely through globalization and technological advancement, and also offers an immersive gaming experience intended to promote an idealized version of the Indonesian national identity. In order to do so, they included in the game elements of the Indonesian culture and history with the almost pedagogical intent to present them in a better version and educate players on how they should think about their own country. Both games, despite being different in terms of genre, development, and production resources, are to be seen as valid configurations of DN in the video game field. Nevertheless, these differences are precisely the reason why they were chosen to adequately depict the multifaced nature of DN. Their parallel analysis allows to comfortably conclude that nationalism in video games is not displayed within a fixed pattern or recurring format, instead there is a variety of conditions in which it can appear.

As this paper intended demonstrate that the same model of DN can be successfully applied to the Chinese context, the game *Glorious Mission* was presented as a suitable case study as it fulfils all the relative requirements with regard to gameplay mechanism, cultural representation and narrative construction. Being a Chinese-made, first person shooting (FPS), online military-themed game, *Glorious Mission* already belongs to a genre in which, as already mentioned, DN easily proliferates. As the first Chinese-made game of this kind, the creators’ efforts to prioritize the use of innovative gaming technology in the game’s development also shows the nationalistic ambition to rival foreign competitors and enhance China’s status in this field. The fact that the entire development team only included Chinese professionals and military experts was also proudly emphasized as it implied that the game is a fully domestic-made project.

Moreover, *Glorious Mission* was heavily impacted by the role of the People’s Liberation Army in terms of development and narrative, as it provided its military expertise, battle simulation technology and most importantly its nationalistic ideological disposition. On

the gameplay side, the PLA's contribution was meant to offer an accurate as much as idealistic representation of the Chinese Army by incorporating realistic details of military life and combat. Whereas, on the narrative side, the nationalistic and patriotic tone of the game was significantly incorporated in its storylines as well as in its public image. National defense is the dominating topic throughout the whole game, but a particular focus is given to China's actual history with Japan. Two of the game's expansions are dedicated to as many sensitive historical issues that have marked the long-standing relation between the two countries and are responsible for a considerable anti-Japanese sentiment existing in China, namely the Second Sino-Japanese War and the territorial dispute over the Diaoyu Islands. In both cases the militaristic and patriotic terminology used shows the attempt to provide a narrative that goes along with the Chinese perspective on those issues, such as the reference to China's 'Century of Humiliation' and the invitation to fight for the defense of the country.

The second theoretical perspective I applied involves the concept of NTN, as it allowed me to analyze another side of the relation between nationalism and technology in China. Unlike DN, that is related to new forms of nationalism emerging in the very use of technology itself, NTN focuses on the external systematic aspects of the matter. It defines nationalism in the form of public policies related to the strategic exploitation of new technologies and aiming to enhance the international competitiveness of domestic tech-related industries. As it was introduced as a hybrid policy between techno-nationalism and technoglobalism, NTN involves the leveraging of globalization through a certain degree of controlled and limited openness to foreign actors with the ultimate aim to introduce cutting-edge technologies and boost domestic innovation. The driving forces in this dynamic are both the public and private sector, usually collaborating through the implementation of specifically designed governmental programs. The growing economic success of the video game industry worldwide, in addition to its potential as a cultural tool of soft power, made it one of the sectors in the high-tech field that are being increasingly regulated by NTN's policies.

Hence, based on the assumption prescribed by NTN, I found that it is an appropriate theoretical approach to study the Chinese policymaking strategy in the field of technology and, particularly, video games. China, in fact, fits the NTN model as a rising state-led economy with the political ambition of enhancing its international status by shifting from "world's factory" to global economic power. The Chinese Communist Party's (CCP) invasive role in the economy is thus legitimized by the need to boost economic growth, but also to reduce its

economic reliance on foreign countries and prevent the risk of cultural penetration commonly associated to globalization.

However, the deep socio-economic transformations occurring in China over the last decades and involving new capitalistic logics, created a contrast between China's new nationalistic goals and its traditional socialist values. Based on my analysis of the Chinese video game market, I found that it exhibits peculiar characteristics due to the country's history, social values and political culture that make it particularly susceptible to those contradictions. These attributes of the Chinese society, in fact, have always affected its NTN policies towards the gaming market, making them dualistic and contentious in nature and distinguishing it from analogue cases in other countries. What emerges is an apparently contradictory picture that sees a promoted, growing and praised video game industry on the one hand and, on the other, a demonization and systematic control over this media.

The grounds for such contradictions are to be found in the cultural and historical context in which video games were introduced and developed in China. At its early stage, the Chinese gaming market was dominated by foreign players importing their products, particularly game consoles and arcade games, by taking advantage of Deng Xiaoping's "open-door policy". The entertaining nature of video games quickly led to their stigmatization as highly pathological, as they were accused of distracting children from their studies and inducing moral decay. The only exceptions were cases such as the gaming system *Xiǎo Bàwáng* from the Chinese company Subor, advertised as a learning platform to enhance the kids' computer literacy and thus positively valued for contributing to the patriotic efforts toward the modernization of society. The general attitude towards video games started to improve in the 1990s, since they were being revalued as instrumental to the country's nationalistic ambitions of economic growth. The duality between their perceived pathological nature and their economic potential was now emerging notably and it has substantially characterized the debate around the gaming industry in China ever since.

In the following decades the Chinese video game market grew exponentially, to the point that it developed a unique self-supporting business model where PC games first and later on mobile games significantly prevailed on console-based platforms, which are instead the most popular in other industrialized countries. As their success and popularity continued to be accompanied by a perception of video games as extrinsic to traditional social values and conducive of pathological behavior, the government's nationalistic action varied accordingly. Beijing have been implementing rigid restrictions and regulations to counteract gaming

addiction and exert a high control over games' ideological content. Nevertheless, despite the systematic attempt to address the pressing social concerns over the pathological risks of gaming, the Chinese leadership has also integrated the online gaming technology into its expanding NTN policies and increasingly seized the opportunity to use it to sustain economic growth. Given that video games have been a largely imported technology for many years, in fact, the production of Chinese-made games specifically targeting the Chinese market is seen as part of the strategy to prevent Western cultural penetration and enhance the country's economic prominence and competitiveness. As a result of this analysis, I argue that the coexistence of these two contradicting views towards video games is the main factor that has influenced China's NTN on the gaming market and that will likely continue to drive it in the future. Both views are, in fact, the product of nationalistic interests: one towards economic prosperity and the other towards the preservation of traditional social values.

In conclusion, on the basis of the above investigation, it can be asserted that an analysis of the Chinese video game industry carried out in accordance to the concepts of Digital Nationalism and Neo-techno-nationalism is more than appropriate. Moreover, the results demonstrate that the growing entanglement between nationalism and technology in terms of identity formation and policymaking already established in other contexts can also be confirmed for the Chinese case. Nevertheless, this work also enriches the current literature and theory of the online game industry and of nationalism by adding new insights of the Chinese context and innovatively using the two theoretical concepts in combination with each other. As this approach is just a first step towards a fully accurate and comprehensive understanding the nationalistic dimension of the Chinese gaming industry, it certainly deserves further consideration by scholars in social and political studies. Since the Chinese gaming industry is relatively recent, future comparative studies could consider the similarities and differences with other prominent gaming industries, both culturally similar like Korea or diametrically different like the United States.

Also, as an interdisciplinary type of research, the potential developments are very promising as they might involve a wide range of study fields, from psychology to sociology. In particular, the above-mentioned interaction between the growing economic success of the video game industry and the social concern over gaming addiction also has the potential to be a baseline for future studies. Even though the latter aspect might be easily identified by external observers as a healthcare issue which has little relation with nationalism, I believe that it actually reveals a more complex issue. Chinese authorities and, in general, video games

critics in China sporadically mention the children's health as the main issue, instead their judgment appears to be more morally driven. As a matter of fact, the government's measures addressing the problem exclusively focus on the material aspect, meaning video game platforms, and are merely limited to a reduction of children's gaming time. Thus, the debate never really considers the public health dimension of the topic: it doesn't involve an attempt to raise awareness on the psychological side effects of gaming or on mental health in general. Similarly, the sociological root causes for such abuse of video games from young people, that choose them over sociality, do not seem to be addressed at all. Chinese parents that seem to be in favor of the restrictions, in fact, believe they are useful to discipline children and help them to focus on their studies and are also appreciative towards the government for stepping in and taking responsibility on this matter (interviews with parents from Southern Metropolis Daily and Asian Boss, 2021).

Furthermore, the fact that gamers of any age started to spend increasingly more time on other online platforms such as live streaming platforms, where they can watch people streaming their gameplay, puts the topic of gaming addiction under a different analytical perspective. It could be questioned, for example, whether the addiction actually comes from the act of gaming itself or, instead, if it has to do with the infrastructures of online technologies. A more in-depth analysis of the issue might at least be useful to distinguish one case from the other, so that any regulation can be designed accordingly. Blindly pointing fingers against video games and simply demonizing this media, instead of looking at the underlying causes, could turn out to be a superficial and ineffective move. This remark could offer a relevant input to further explore the cause-effect relationship between gaming and pathological behavior and investigate the controversial policymaking practices applied in China and other countries in this regard.

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